

Climateurope2

Task 2.2

D2.2 Preliminary best practices in provenance of processing methodology to guarantee traceability and reproducibility of climate data and ways to communicate it in a user-friendly manner

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Executive summary

The document offers a multilevel landscape on the requirements and challenges associated with traceability and transparency of data and processes in the context of climate services. We start by reporting on the relevance and attention that the FAIR and Research Data communities are giving to the problem of traceability and provenance (Section 2). This is then brought up in the context of international organisations that are largely concerned with the dissemination of climate information, such as the IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change) and WMO (World Meteorological Organisation) (Section 3). Here we discuss their need for transparency, particularly targeting the dissemination of trustworthy climate change assessment reports, as well as the procedures to communicate changes occurring in the climate data products.

In Section 4, we take a step back and try to clarify general definitions to better characterise the different types of provenance, the answers they solve and their role in the data exploitation practices. The implementation of these definitions can find support by standardisation efforts, which we report on in Section 5, including the technical elements that aim at lowering the barriers for their adoptions. Finally, in Section 6, we present a collection of climate services and tools that are already adopting the standards. These endeavours take place within independent national organisations, as well as collaborative partnerships in the EU, such as IS-ENES. In some cases we also demonstrate how these services integrate with each other and share the provenance information generated during their interactions. The document ends with concluding discussions, towards the continuation of a collaborative strategy to produce a sound, concrete and priority driven guidance to traceability.

1. Introduction

Provenance in the context of climate services involves documenting and tracking the origins and history of data, information, and processes used to generate climate-related products obtained from the available services. The rationale for incorporating provenance in climate services encompasses several critical aspects. It covers an essential role for ensuring the reliability and quality of climate data and services (Baldissera Pacchetti et al. 2021) [23]. It allows users to evaluate the credibility and accuracy of the information, enabling informed decision-making in climate-related matters (Cash et al. 2003) [21]. The dissemination of climate data benefits from developing trust, by revealing its sources and detailing the processing or modification it has undergone. Users gain confidence in the data they rely on.

During the production of this deliverable some of the authors contributed to the review of the WMO Climate Data Management Specifications, which helped to elaborate those use cases where traceability finds a concrete application. Here we separated concepts of lineage and history of changes (ie. Versioning). We also report the experience of IPCC, where priorities focus on facilitating the retrieval of the main assets involved in the generation of the reports' Figures (final data and software), as well as attribution of authorship and roles of the different actors involved in the generation and curation of a particular dataset.

The use cases presented highlight that collaboration among different organisations and researchers working on climate-related issues will be enhanced through provenance. A sound implementation of provenance based solutions will allow them to understand each other's methods and data sources, leading to more effective and coordinated efforts. Researchers can build upon the work of others more effectively when they have a clear understanding of the data and methodologies used in previous studies. It serves as a fundamental component for the effective use and development of climate-related products and services, aiding both decision-makers and researchers in addressing climate-related challenges.

2. Provenance Contribution to FAIRness and impact on Users

Concerning its exploitation, provenance facilitates the reuse and replication of results and the ability to reproduce climate analyses and services. Thereby contributes to the **Reusability** principle of FAIR. It guarantees that the steps and data used to create a particular climate product can be reconstructed, verified, and repeated by other researchers or organisations. However, to obtain concrete replication and reproducibility, it is required combining provenance, which is fundamentally a knowledge-base, with tools, data and software repositories, and technical components that foster reproducibility. This also requires the availability of a computational infrastructure, whose connectivity and resources are sized and suitable to enact the reproducibility mechanisms. Nonetheless, an agreed level of

transparency that provides insights into the sources, methodologies, and potential biases associated with the data and services, is also important for validation, accountability and scrutiny.

In the Research Data Alliance (RDA), some effort has taken place to discuss the principles and the guidelines with respect to Provenance and FAIRness. The FAIR Data Maturity Model¹ and its specification and guidelines mention provenance requirements in the metadata:

- R1.2 RDA-R1.2-01M
 - Metadata includes provenance information according to community-specific standards

RDA-R1.2-01M Metadata includes provenance information according to community-specific standards
Principle – as defined by GO FAIR – to which the indicator relates
This indicator is linked to the following principle: <i>R1.2: (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance</i> . More information about that principle can be found here .
Description of the indicator RDA-R1.2-01M
This indicator requires the metadata to include information about the provenance of the data, i.e. information about the origin, history or workflow that generated the data, in a way that is compliant with the standards that are used in the community in which the data is produced.
Assessment details
The indicator can be evaluated by verifying that the provenance information follows the community standard. A RDA-endorsed service like FAIRsharing could be helpful to identify the relevant standards.

- R1.2 RDA-R1.2-02M
 - Metadata includes provenance information according to a cross-community language

1

https://www.rd-alliance.org/system/files/FAIR%20Data%20Maturity%20Model_%20specification%20and%20guidelines_v0.90.pdf

RDA-R1.2-02M Metadata includes provenance information according to a cross-community language

Principle – as defined by GO FAIR – to which the indicator relates

This indicator is linked to the following principle: *R1.2: (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance*. More information about that principle can be found [here](#).

Description of the indicator RDA-R1.2-02M

This indicator requires that the metadata provides provenance information according to a cross-domain language.

Assessment details

The indicator can be evaluated by assessing whether a cross-domain language is used for provenance information (such as [PROV-O](#)).

There is an increasing demand from policy and decision-makers for climate data and information to support adaptation and mitigation decision-making. However, for users trying to navigate a complex scientific landscape, support is needed to help them make best use of climate data and information. Simple guidance to help users evaluate climate knowledge was provided by Cash et al. (2003) [21]. Underpinning this guidance are the ideas of traceability and transparency, not just of the information itself but also of the organisations providing it. Transparency and traceability builds trust informing credibility, as well as helping the user to appreciate the relevance of the information, and therefore assess its saliency. Cash et al. (2003) also suggest that being open and transparent about who has been involved in developing the science, and how will inform the user of the legitimacy of the information. These three criteria - saliency, credibility and legitimacy - have been further discussed in the literature but always with the view that maintaining traceability and transparency are fundamental tenets.

3. International Organisations - Use Cases and approaches to traceability

International organisations are becoming more aware of the importance of embedding transparency and traceability practices in their operations as well as dissemination material, especially when these target a large and differentiated community of end users. We report here use cases and approaches that have been recently brought forward by organisations such as WMO and IPCC. However, we are aware of other initiatives, for instance carried out by C3S (Copernicus Climate Change Service), which aimed at preliminary assessments of their traceability mechanisms. These were conducted in the context of a Copernicus contract², and focussed on internal investigations on the coverage and completeness of the traceability information associated with the CDS (Climate Data Store) toolbox³.

² <https://climate.copernicus.eu/c3s512-quality-assurance-climate-data-store>

³ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!toolbox>

3.1. WMO: Climate Data Management Specification and Use Case

At the time of writing this report, WMO is updating the Climate Data Management Specifications⁴, published in 2014. In the new version particular attention is given to the requirements for a provenance management system that should be implemented at an operational Climate Service. To facilitate that, WMO proposes a concrete use case concerning a data-recovery scenario for a weather station that experiences a breakdown in telecommunications.

This and other use cases, alongside preliminary discussions over provenance, were introduced during a workshop between the WMO Expert Team on Data Requirements for Climate Services, and the CE2 team involved in the production of this deliverable. The event was held on the 7th of December 2023⁵, with the purpose to trigger a series of small forums on the topic, as stated in the document introducing the initiative⁶. Internationally, WMO is the leading actor providing guidance on climate related data management. The development and adoption of standards are often driven by WMO through working groups delivering documents and guidelines that are at the centre of discussion about quality climate services, involving relevant expertise from the weather and climate community.

The case study that we report in this section, assumes that a lack of connectivity caused that values were not transmitted to the Meteorological headquarters for 10 days across August and September, requiring the data operations department to apply appropriate techniques to estimate the missing values. This to comply with the commitments of providing users with daily and monthly evapotranspiration calculations for this (and any other) station. The use case specifies also that the estimation of the values for 10 daily evapotranspiration values and the monthly evapotranspiration value for August, is implemented using a reliable and documented scientific procedure.

According to the current practices in terms of the organisation of the acquired stations' data, the estimation will affect 11 data items (10 daily and 1 monthly) which can be sent to users on time with the appropriate precautions.

Once the Meteorological institute receives the raw data from the station. This can be used to correct the missing records, as follows

1. Replace the missing data with the retrieved raw data, consistently with the start and end date of the gap.
2. Update the WIGOS⁷ metadata for these raw data
3. Restart the data control chain for these raw data
4. Create and modify the **provenance** and **lineage** data for this raw data.
5. Recalculate the daily and monthly evapotranspiration for these 11 datasets
6. Create and modify the **provenance** and **lineage** data for these 11 datasets
7. Notify users that the daily and monthly evapotranspiration values for these stations and dates have been changed.

⁴<https://library.wmo.int/records/item/51447-climate-data-management-system-specifications#.YM7fBOZMdr>

⁵<https://github.com/ET-DRC/Home/wiki/Draft-agenda:-ET-DRC-meeting,-6%E2%80%908-December-2023.-Geneva.-Switzerland>

⁶<https://github.com/ET-DRC/Home/files/13544350/Provenance.workshop.series.pdf>

⁷<https://community.wmo.int/en/activity-areas/WIGOS>

In such a case study it may seem easy to gather information which will be able to answer the following questions, for instance as part of the description of a new version of the dataset(s).

- What has changed? (eg. what part of the data)
- Why was it changed?
- Who/what changed it?
- On whose behalf did they act?
- When was it changed?
- Who was responsible?

However, more challenging will be to capture details of the underlying process that updated the gap, since technical details concerning points 3 and 5 need to be recorded as lineage information, thereby needing automated mechanisms to do so. In such a way the questions below might be answered.

- How was the raw data processed?
- How was the daily and monthly data processed?

Combining the information collected to answer the question above, will give the opportunity to fill in change-log records answering the following questions.

- How was it changed?
- What was done to change it?

These contribute to completing the historical record describing the updated release of a particular dataset, to which a new version tag could be potentially assigned, a DOI landing page reporting Errata information, depending on the local meteorological data management policies.

3.2. IPCC: Traceability and Reproducibility of AR Figures

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) primarily produces assessment reports and summaries of climate science, impacts, adaptation and mitigation strategies. The TG-Data Working group⁸, aims to provide guidance to the IPCC's Data Distribution Centre (DDC) on curation, traceability, stability, availability and transparency of data and scenarios related to the reports of the IPCC. A preliminary collection of guidelines [2] was produced to introduce to the authors and the Technical Support Units (TSU) associated with the chapters of the report. These introduced general FAIR principles and provided indication on the particular solutions that could be used to implement them. As an outcome, the authors of the assessment reports chapters applied the principles to obtain the traceability and reproducibility of the most important figures published in the report. This effort is aimed at disclosing the source data and the tooling used to produce the derived plots, allowing others to reuse these in an informed way. This small but initial step is important to complement the transparent and rigorous scientific review process that ensures the credibility of the IPCC assessments. Publishing the technical details related to the code and data used to produce graphics or

⁸ <https://www.ipcc.ch/data/>

synthesise results, thereby making them findable and reusable, enhances the adoption and trust in the integrity of the climate data within society.

In AR6, the information was captured without the support of any formal model. Metadata were agreed within the working group and shared with the authors who, upon the curation and archival of the published assets, contributed to provide the needed information in different ways (eg. documents, spreadsheets), which was then validated by the technical units.

The different working groups rely on data repositories to store and curate the assets behind the figures, being these derived products or collections. Authors and support personnel then use Git repositories to manage the source code generating the figures. This code was often produced in the form of executable Jupyter notebooks, with indication of the underlying software environment and data used.

Finally, the readers of the reports have access to different ways to recollect the information behind a figure. For instance they can find dedicated tables included in the Supplementary Material (Figure 1) or more interactive web pages associated with a particular report, as shown in Figure 2.

7.SM.7 Data Table

Table 7.SM.14 | Input data table. Input datasets and code used to create chapter figures.

Figure Number	Dataset/Code Name	Type	File Name/Specificities	License Type	Dataset/Code Citation	Dataset/Code URL	Related Publications
Box 7.2, Figure 1		Code	notebooks/350_chapter7_box7.2_fig1.ipynb	MIT		https://github.com/IPCC-WG1/Chapter-7 (accessed 28/01/2022)	
		Data	data_input/fig7.1_box7.2/			https://github.com/IPCC-WG1/Chapter-7 (accessed 28/01/2022)	
Figure 7.3		Code	notebooks/300_chapter7_fig7.3.ipynb	MIT		https://github.com/IPCC-WG1/Chapter-7 (accessed 28/01/2022)	
		Data	data_input/Loeb_et_al_2020			https://github.com/IPCC-WG1/Chapter-7 (accessed 28/01/2022)	Loeb et al. (2020)
Figure 7.4		Code	notebooks/270_chapter7_fig7.4.ipynb	MIT	Smith et al. (2021)	https://github.com/IPCC-WG1/Chapter-7 (accessed 28/01/2022)	

Figure 1. Table of the Supplementary Material of IPCC AR6 Chapter 7. The table indicates, for each Figure of the Chapter, the location of the repositories containing the data and software used for its generation, including citations details and related publications.

Figure SPM.8

Figure caption

Figure SPM.8 | Selected indicators of global climate change under the five illustrative scenarios used in this Report

The projections for each of the five scenarios are shown in colour. Shades represent uncertainty ranges – more detail is provided for each panel below. The black curves represent the historical simulations (panels a, b, c) or the observations (panel d). Historical values are included in all graphs to provide context for the projected future changes.

Panel (a) Global surface temperature changes in °C relative to 1850–1900. These changes were obtained by combining Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) model simulations with observational constraints based on past simulated warming, as well as an updated assessment of equilibrium climate sensitivity (see Box SPM.1). Changes relative to 1850–1900 based on 20-year averaging periods are calculated by adding 0.85°C (the observed global surface temperature increase from 1850–1900 to 1995–2014) to simulated changes relative to 1995–2014. *Very likely* ranges are shown for SSP1-2.6 and SSP3-7.0.

Panel (b) September Arctic sea ice area in 10⁶ km² based on CMIP6 model simulations. *Very likely* ranges are shown for SSP1-2.6 and SSP3-7.0. The Arctic is projected to be practically ice-free near mid-century under intermediate and high

Figure 2. Interactive page describing one of the fundamental figures of the Summary Report for Policy Makers⁹.

From 2013, similar efforts have been pursued in the US for the National Climate Assessment¹⁰. Together with IPCC these practices represent an important step towards obtaining full transparency of the reports on climate change that are made available to the public.

The IPCC central repository curating the data¹¹, further extends the provenance information by providing insights, when available, on the *Purpose* (where the data used), the *Source* (where it can be found), and the *Processing and Treatment* it went through. This could benefit from adopting standard vocabularies and formal data models, thereby offering a consistent representation and interpretation for each of the datasets used in the report. Figure 3 shows a view of the provenance information associated with the data behind the image SPM.8, which we previously discussed and shown in Figure 2. Finally, the IPCC Interactive Atlas¹² has developed a more technical approach to enable the actual reproducibility of the figure produced by this service. This has been realised after a thorough review of the Atlas *GitHub* repository [1], which is now offering the means to validate, replicate and programmatically adjust the plots, which would have been otherwise only available interactively, via the online service or as part of the published reports. TG-Data already produced a document illustrating a refined collection of FAIR recommendations [3] for the new assessment report (AR7). Here the requirement for provenance is reinforced to all static products recorded in the DDC catalogue, foreseeing the availability of interactive tools to export provenance information, including references to input or intermediate data

⁹ <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/figures/summary-for-policymakers/figure-spm-8>

¹⁰ <https://www.globalchange.gov/highlights/tracing-global-change-science-back-source>

¹¹ <https://ipcc-browser.ipcc-data.org/browser/search>

¹² <https://interactive-atlas.ipcc.ch/>

as well as source code. Essentially, all material required to review these IPCC products should be made available, so that they can be reviewed as part of the AR process.

Provenance

Purpose: Data used by Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) authors and supplied for archiving to MetadataWorks Ltd by the Technical Support Unit (TSU) for IPCC Working Group III (WG III).

Source:
AR6 WGIII Chapters 6-11, 17

Chapter 6: 6.4.2, 6.7.7, Box 6.1, Figure 6.18
Chapter 7 Sections- 7.3, 7.4, 7.5, 7.6
Chapter 8 Sections- 8.2, 8.4, 8.6
Chapter 9 Sections- 9.4, 9.5, 9.8, Table 9.5
Chapter 10 Sections- 10.3, 10.4, 10.5, 10.6, 10.8, Table 10.3
Chapter 11 Sections- 11.5.3
Chapter 12: 12.5
Chapter 17 Supplementary material table 17.1

Data processing or treatment:

The sectoral chapters (Chapters 6-11) assessed the literature in terms of the impacts of each of the shortlisted sectoral mitigation options on the 17 United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

This assessment is qualitatively and uses three signs:

- '+' to denote positive interaction only (synergies) between mitigation option and the SDG,
- '-' to denote negative interaction only (trade-offs) between mitigation option and the SDG and
- '+' to denote mixed interactions between mitigation option and the SDG.

In some cases, where there is gap in literature, these are left blank denoting that these impacts have not been assessed in the literature.

To support these signs, brief statements are provided followed by uncertainty qualifiers in the supplementary table of Chapter 17. These uncertainty qualifiers denote the confidence levels (low, medium and high). The assessment also recognises that the interactions between mitigation options and the SDGs are context-specific and depends on scale, so a detailed explanation on context specificity/scale is provided in the supplementary table of Chapter 17.

Figure 3. Example of provenance information stored by the IPCC Data Distribution Center at <https://ipcc-data.org>

4. Types of Provenance

4.1. Lineage and Provenance in Data Management

Data lineage is the process of tracking the path of data from its original sources and all the intermediate transformations it undergoes. It encompasses the entire journey of data, starting from its inception and tracing its progression over time. By establishing data lineage, one gains insight into the analytics processes, effectively creating a roadmap that elucidates the journey data takes from its source to the ultimate user. This comprehensive view encompasses the various processes data undergoes, including transformations, aggregations, and other manipulations. The utility of data lineage extends to performing root cause analysis, error tracking, enhancing data quality, and ensuring adherence to regulatory requirements.

Conversely, data provenance places a greater emphasis on the historical documentation of data encompassing records to incorporate information like *data authorship*, *creation timestamps*, *modification history*, and *the identities responsible for those alterations*.

While data lineage offers a broad overview of data's path, data provenance delves further into the details of its historical trail (ie. by linking different versions), focusing on data's authenticity and integrity.

To facilitate the understanding of this distinction, we can summarise the main differences of these two concepts.

	Data Lineage	Data Provenance
Definition	Tracks the life-cycle of data, including its origins and movements over time.	Records the data's historical background, providing a comprehensive account of its origins and how it was derived from its original state.
Focus	Concentrates on the journey and transformations of data.	Focuses on the data's history, credibility, and trustworthiness.
Answers Questions Like	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Where did the data originate 2. What transformations has it undergone before the present state? 3. Where does it move next? 4. Who uses it? 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Who created the data and when? 2. What changes have been made to the data and by whom? 3. What is the original source of the data?
Use Cases	Applied for conducting root cause analysis, error tracking, enhancing data quality, and ensuring adherence to regulatory standards..	Used to verify data authenticity, confirming data's trustworthiness, preserving data integrity, and offering a comprehensive historical context.

Level of Detail	Broad perspective on the path data takes and the processes it undergoes.	Comprehensive details of the data's historical evolution and modifications.
Importance in Data Management	Essential for the understanding of data movement, interconnections, and the effects of alterations	Crucial for upholding the quality, integrity, and reliability of data.

Let's consider as a concrete example, data versioning. Its best practices involve assigning unique identifiers or labels to different versions of data. Tracking changes, managing different states, and understanding the evolution of the data over time. This includes recording when those changes occurred, and who made them. Here authorship provides accurate attribution at different stages of data creation, processing, or analysis involving multiple individuals. Data provenance as defined in the table would provide all the needed information to make versioning complete, thereby allowing users to understand the history and evolution of a dataset. Data Lineage instead, gathers details on the flow and transformations of data, showing its path from its initial acquisition of the published product. It is typically supported by visual representations that can graphically document the journey the data takes. Ultimately, more versions of the same data retain different lineage traces. Especially for derived products, each release typically undergoes reprocessing stages, which may involve, for instance, gap filling of the raw data, corrections to the metadata records, reprojections and aggregations.

4.2. Provenance of Processing Pipelines

In this section we consider the particular, yet common scenario, where data acquisition and manipulation operations occur via computational pipelines (or workflows), which are conveniently represented as DAGs (Directed Acyclic Graphs). Assuming such structure, a substantial amount of literature has looked at Prospective provenance as a particular type of provenance to capture and tell the history of the variations of a processing graph [6]. Prospective provenance keeps track of changes applied to both parameterisation and structure of the pipeline, and it should also include information on the underlying computation environments [5]. This type of provenance is extremely important to validate, reuse and improve acquisition and preprocessing operations, especially when the ownership and responsibility are handed over to third parties. This also facilitates updated data products to be evaluated based on the evidence brought by previous executions.

It is necessary to identify enough details to refer and describe the source-code used for the implementation of the scientific methods and its dependencies, such as the set of libraries, interpreters and all of the sensible information associated with it. Curated catalogues of software, virtual images or docker-based containers, should be maintained by institutional organisations to assure that operations could be reproduced in the same or at least emulated environments.

In this context the information showing the progressive effects on the data takes the name of Retrospective Provenance. This concept is similar to the Data Lineage previously introduced, and it may offer views on computational details collected at run-time that have an impact on the final products. Formal representations of combined prospective and retrospective provenance that adopt generic provenance models exist and are inspired by the characteristic of scientific workflows [4]. Modern data processing system developed by the industry¹³ took inspiration from the literature and adopted the convenient graph representation to better orchestrate data production chains, obtaining implicitly a substantial amount of provenance information. However, tooling is still limited and the implementation is often based on experimental solutions¹⁴.

5. Technical Elements

5.1. Data Models and Standards

Approaches to provenance collection and representation used in specific settings start to proliferate. These often adopt ad-hoc formats, rely on general logs and often do not take into account mappings to existing standards. Although several of these implementations may already collect sensible information that would enable the traceability of data and operations, one question remains.

*How can the provenance of the collection of climate data and the software used to manipulate it be best modelled and in the future, found via the Internet? The resolution of this issue will be of relevance to many domains.*¹⁵

5.1.1. Lineage in ISO 19115

ISO 19115-1 and ISO 19115-2 are international standards developed by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) that define metadata for geographic information.

While ISO 19115-1 establishes the essential elements, terms, and definitions that are used in describing geographic information and services, its extended release (19115-2) accommodates specific requirements for describing imagery and gridded data, besides adding further details in support of more accurate descriptions.

These standards play a crucial role in ensuring consistency and interoperability in the description of geographic information, making it easier to share and exchange spatial data across different platforms

¹³ <https://airflow.apache.org/>

¹⁴ <https://airflow.apache.org/docs/apache-airflow/stable/administration-and-deployment/lineage.html>

¹⁵ <https://www.w3.org/2021/sdw/UseCases/SDWUseCasesAndRequirements.html#ProvenanceOfClimateData>

and organisations. They also contain a basic notion of provenance which is mainly targeted to lineage information. This is represented through the use of specific elements. Here are key components and extensions, related to lineage in these standards:

- **LI_Lineage**: This element is part of the ISO 19115-1 standard and represents the lineage or history of the dataset. Its extension **LE_Lineage** adds additional lineage/quality information relating to, Processing and Process Steps, Algorithms, Source(s).
- **LE_Processing** includes **LE_Algorithm** and adds information to describe the procedure by which the algorithm is applied to generate the product.
- **LE_ProcessStep**: This element added in 19115-2 is used to describe individual process steps involved in creating, modifying, or processing the data. It includes details such as the description of the process, the date and time of execution, and references to the sources used.
- **LI_Source**, extends **LE_Source**, is introduced to describe the output of a process step that includes imagery details.
- **LE_ProcessStepReport** was added to identify external information about the processing steps.
- **LE_Algorithm** is added to describe the methodology used to derive the data from the source data.

In Figure 4 [19] we report a graphical representation on how some of the ISO elements are used in a combined description of a processing workflow.

Figure 4. Representation of ISO 19115 and 19115-2 lineage models to depict a complete sequence of a processing workflow.

One of the shortcomings of the ISO model is that it allows the description of sources geospatial entities, thereby limiting a detailed characterisation of additional input parameters, which are so far only allowed in the form of literals, precluding any further detail. Efforts to overcome this limitation by combining and importing elements from other standards have been uptaken in the literature [19], with the additional proposals to further extend the standard with semantic elements that capture the complete history of an experimental campaign targeting a particular dataset.

5.1.2. W3C PROV and Templates

Another possible answer to the question of how to represent provenance information in a way that can be universally distributed and interpreted over the internet, is provided by the widely-used W3C's PROV recommendation¹⁶.

This standard evolved from the Open Provenance Model (OPM) [7], and has been adopted in both production and experimental settings by several domains. The formalisation and the technical formats adopted for its representation makes it very suitable for the digital and interoperable dissemination of provenance information through the web, as well as its integration with other models, thanks to its large adoption of semantic web standards.

In Figure 5, we show the essential elements of the PROV data-model. These consist of three primary classes with unique and mandatory identifiers and nine properties to describe the relations between the classes. The three classes are `prov:Entity` which is the central concept and represents resources, `prov:Activity` representing actions performed upon entities, and `prov:Agent` representing persons or machines who bears some form of responsibility for an activity.

Figure 5: Schema of the essential elements of the PROV data-model: Activities inform other Activities by means of an exchange of information and they generate and use Entities. Entities can be derived from other Entities. Respectively, they are associated and attributed to Agents, who perform or delegate an action. Image obtained from the PROV online documentation.

The most important relationships are: *used* (an activity used some artefact), *wasAssociatedWith* (an agent participated in some activity), *wasGeneratedBy* (an activity generated an entity), *wasDerivedFrom* (an entity was derived from another entity), *wasAttributedTo* (an entity was attributed to an agent), *actedOnBehalfOf* (an agent acted on behalf of another agent) and *wasInformedBy* (an activity used an entity produced by another activity). The model can be further extended by including **Expanded terms**, used to specialise agents and entities to a particular domain, as well as **Qualified terms**, used to provide additional attributes of the binary relations, as described by the formal specification of the

¹⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-overview/>.

PROV Ontology¹⁷. We will go through some specialisations of the model in the implementation section.

Generic Interactive tools to handle and share PROV documents online, are available via the services provided by *openprovenance.org*¹⁸. However, the capturing of provenance information, coupled with the generation of PROV compliant documents within a software system, often requires ad hoc implementations which increases complexity and thereby it may hinder the adoption of the model. Although there are software libraries that help the generation of PROV documents, most recently there has been a growing interest into decoupling further the collection of provenance details from the actual formalisation, aiming at improving the dialog that lead to the design of provenance scenarios, which foster reusability besides simplifying the technical implementation.

Figure 6. Integration schema of the PROV-Template technology in a generic application.

This idea led to the PROV-Template [8] specification, which is supported by a technical framework including software libraries and services. It revolves around the concept of separation of concerns in the designing of models for the desired provenance information. The templates incorporate variables, which are subsequently filled with relevant data extracted from existing process output. Templates are documents encoded in PROV-N syntax. They describe recurrent provenance patterns, which are instantiated by passing the template and a template's variables binding document to a template-expansion algorithm. Templates facilitate the modelling of re-usable provenance scenarios (generalisation vs tailoring), and remove the burden to hardcode formal provenance editing in the computational tools. This task is delegated to template expansion tools and services, see Figure 6, such as the ProvToolbox¹⁹ and the ProvTemplateCatalogue²⁰, respectively. Thereby, changes to the template might not affect the tool's source code, except in those circumstances when the updated

¹⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

¹⁸ <https://openprovenance.org/>

¹⁹ <https://lucmoreau.github.io/ProvToolbox/>

²⁰ <https://github.com/EnvriPlus-PROV/ProvTemplateCatalog>

template introduces new variables, which are usually relatively easy to add to the binding document. The adoption of templates has been explored across different communities [10], and their adoption to capture and manage provenance of computational contexts has been applied to real systems [9], one of which will be introduced in the implementation section.

5.2. Use of Identifiers

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) play a crucial role in data provenance by providing a stable and unique way to identify and reference digital objects, ensuring traceability and facilitating the management of provenance information. They can be implemented as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)²¹ or Handle²², and serve as a gateway to associated metadata, and contribute long-term accessibility of data in research and scholarly communication. Their uniqueness ensures that each digital object has a distinct identifier, avoiding conflicts and enabling reliable referencing.

For instance, DataCite²³ associated with DOI provenance metadata describing the history of a particular DOI metadata record, i.e. what changes were made when and by whom. The information is stored and provided via an API and adopts for its interoperable representation the PROV vocabulary, previously introduced.

In more advanced implementations, humans, as well as machines, can follow the PID, to access information about the data's provenance, which can be itself characterised by a network of interlinked identifiers, associated with operations, types, and clients, as we will show in the example below. This model of use is also pursued by the FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs)²⁴, although it relies on a particular protocol which is still in development, the Digital Object Interfacing Protocol (DOIP)²⁵.

Some of the climate datasets available to the community are already managed following similar concepts, and thereby are typically assigned a persistent identifier (PID). PIDs ensure that these datasets are findable and citable by providing them with a unique reference.

As an example, in this section we will consider this aspect applied to the use case on climate data analytics workflows (see Ophidia & yProv Section). In that particular use case there are two different types of PIDs that are managed:

- external PIDs: used for input/output datasets (e.g., CMIP* datasets). They are usually generated by PID services, like in the case of CMIP5 and CMIP6 experiments and can be inferred from experiment catalogues (i.e. ESGF Search for CMIP experiments)..

²¹ <https://www.doi.org/>

²² <https://www.handle.net/>

²³ <https://datacite.org>

²⁴ <https://fairdo.org/1316-2/>

²⁵ <https://www.cordra.org/documentation/api/doip.html>

- internal PIDs: unique persistent identifiers attached to intermediate products (i.e., Ophidia datacubes) that are managed as in-memory objects. An example is reported in Figure 7. Their lifetime is constrained to the specific user’s session and their corresponding PID is self-generated by the specific Ophidia instance that is hosting the workflow. This is done for performance reasons (mostly scalability). It is worth mentioning here that final products of an analysis could still be stored on the filesystem and published to some file server (getting an “external” PID via a PID Handle System), that is, it could potentially become a persistent object published on the web.

Figure 7. Example of internal PIDs in Ophidia

6. Implementations in the climate community

6.1. IPCC Atlas and METACLIP

As already introduced earlier in this document, the Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) [22] from the IPCC has embraced the FAIR Guiding Principles. Particularly, the Atlas chapter of Working Group I (WGI) introduced an open-source repository as result from a thorough review process performed by experts, aimed at evaluating the transparency and reproducibility of the figures generated by the interactive Atlas²⁶. The repository was then improved, to include coding annotated Jupyter notebooks, data provenance, and a collection of aggregated datasets featured in the Atlas chapter and interactive service. This repository is open for examination by both the scientific community and the general public²⁷, as it contains all the technical elements to enable the reproducibility of the figures, as explained in the associated publication [1].

Technical implementation of data provenance in the Atlas, mostly concern the underlying analysis library, Climate4R, which is a collection of R packages for transparent climate data access,

²⁶ <https://interactive-atlas.ipcc.ch/>

²⁷ <https://github.com/IPCC-WG1/Atlas>

post-processing and visualisation²⁸. The software embeds a provenance module, METACLIP²⁹, with the goal to encode the necessary metadata for ensuring traceability and reproducibility of the climate products, such as data files, plots, and maps (Lineage). The module can be also used to meticulously monitor the operations within often intricate data workflows (Processing Pipelines).

Figure 8. PROV can be extended to represent particular details and semantics, while still allowing mapping between its various specialisations. The example shows mappings between generic workflow and climate specific provenance, such as METACLIP.

METACLIP vocabularies [12] serve as a specialised extension of widely adopted, domain-agnostic data models like PROV. They are crafted to articulate the diverse activities, agents, and transformations integral to the generation of climate data products. Essentially, these vocabularies offer a domain-specific expansion of the PROV data model tailored to the nuances of climate science. In Figure 8 we show how PROV can be actually extended, which also allows the creation of conceptual mappings across different specialisations. The advantage of this, is that PROV can be adapted to adhere to a climate service’s particular vocabularies and traceability priorities, maintaining the capability to be combined with other specialisations. For instance, especially within distributed infrastructure, such flexibility would allow the provenance generated by interconnected systems to be integrated, enabling detailed and automated traceability and validation studies, as well as fostering long term archival.

²⁸ <https://github.com/SantanderMetGroup/climate4R>

²⁹ <http://www.metaclip.org/>

6.2. KNMI Early Warning Center

One of the consequences of a rapidly changing climate is the increased frequency of extreme weather events. That is why the KNMI is building an Early Warning Center (EWC), aimed at providing alert and advice at national level. Provenance can play a crucial role in an early warning centre by enhancing the credibility, reliability, and effectiveness of the warnings issued, Moreover it plays a role in the following aspects.

1. **Continuous Improvement:** By tracking the provenance of warnings, early warning centres can identify areas for improvement in their processes. This feedback loop is essential for continuously enhancing the accuracy and efficiency of the warning systems.
2. **Adaptability to Change:** Provenance allows for easy tracking of changes in data sources, models, and algorithms. This adaptability is crucial in a dynamic environment where new data sources and technologies are constantly emerging.
3. **Communication of Uncertainty:** Early warning systems often deal with uncertainties. Provenance information can help communicate the degree of uncertainty associated with each warning by providing insights into the sources of data and the reliability of models.

This motivated experimental activities aiming at the implementation of a comprehensive provenance infrastructure that adopts standard models and technologies. The outcome delivered a proof of concept based on the PROV-Template specification (Section 5.1.2) and a scalable services architecture to manage provenance produced by run-time analysis tools. The system includes services for storing and expanding the templates, and to store and interrogate the provenance. In this particular case we can refer to provenance as data lineage, thereby providing insights on the transformations and processes involved in the particular analysis delivering EWC products and associated warnings.

Visualisation in GeoWeb - Cell Tracking

Figure 9. Overview of the use of the Provenance API to enable Traceability, Dissemination and Verification of trustworthy warning products.

Figure 9 gives an overview of its main usage scenario. Here, the data and warnings produced by an application that tracks hail storms, *CellTrack*, are visualised on a GeoSpatial weather tool (GeoWeb³⁰). Users could request the lineage information by invoking the provenance API, which exposes the underlying provenance database. This is realised by adopting a general provenance model, which exploits standard vocabularies, as well as custom metadata tailored on the EWC requirements.

With more detail, Figure 10 shows the template developed for the EWC. This is inspired by the PROV-ONE³¹ model, which accommodates prospective and retrospective provenance associated with any type of analysis workflow. However, for the EWC we mostly focus on its retrospective capabilities, embedding EWC custom metadata to represent the different level of warning carried by the output (colourless, yellow, orange, red).

Figure 10. Template of the Provenance model used to capture data lineage and retrospective provenance of the EWC analysis process.

The model captures input data as well as the particular version of the code used to perform the analysis run. This is part of the template's entity typed as *provone:Workflow* and *prov:Plan*, as shown in Figure 10.

30

<https://www.knmi.nl/research/observations-data-technology/projects/geoweb-the-next-generation-web-based-tooling-for-monitoring-the-atmosphere>

31

<http://jenkins-1.dataone.org/jenkins/view/Documentation%20Projects/job/ProvONE-Documentation-trunk/ws/provenance/ProvONE/v1/provone.html>

Concerning the technical infrastructure, the most recent architectural design (Figure 11) involves the adoption of a messaging system to asynchronously route the requests for the expansion and storage of the provenance information. This decoupled approach aims at optimising the overall performance by reducing the impact of latency on highly frequent updates. The storage is delegated to the Neo4j³² graph database, which has been extended by a semantic module that allows the adoption of RDF³³ for the representation of the provenance information.

Figure 11. Asynchronous architecture of the Provenance API Service.

The Provenance API is agnostic of the type of templates used and the provenance information stored in the underlying graph database. However, the database is exposed with a collection of high-level methods for its interrogation, which returns provenance in JSON-LD³⁴ format. This to facilitate the extraction and adoption of provenance data, without necessarily requiring clients to know how to handle queries in the database specific language. The API can be extended by additional interrogation methods, depending on the provenance templates adopted by the different provenance producers. The current implementation supports two types of queries returning, respectively, (1) the lineage of a data product, starting from its ID, and (2) given the ID of a particular execution, the complete list of provenance records describing the data that has been generated. Future work foresees an interactive interrogation and visualisation interface, aimed at enabling visual inspection and summarisation of the largely interconnected and sometimes complex provenance data.

³² <https://neo4j.com/>

³³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/2014/REC-rdf11-concepts-20140225/Overview.html>

³⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/2014/REC-json-ld-20140116/>

6.3. Web Processing Services for ESGF and Copernicus

ROOCS³⁵ is a project to develop data services in support of the Copernicus Climate Change Service³⁶ (C3S). ROOCS provides a collection of tools to provide data-aware processing services of climate projections from CMIP6, CMIP5 and CORDEX.

The main focus of the service is to reduce the volumes of data transferred by providing data-reduction that can be invoked directly from the C3S Climate Data Store (CDS)³⁷. See Figure LL.

ROOCS consists of three main software packages:

- CLISOPS: a Python library based on xarray³⁸ providing operators like subsetting, averaging and regridding on climate data from CMIP6 etc.
- ROOK: An OGC Web Processing Service³⁹ to provide CLISOPS operators as a service to be used by the Climate Data Store. In addition to single operators like subset, it also provides a workflow process to chain the available operations.
- ROOKi: A Python library that simplifies the usage of the ROOK service on the client side.

Figure 12 gives a schematic representation of the current architecture.

Figure 12. Overview of the architecture used by the Climate Data Store.

The ROOK data reduction service returns on each data request also a PROV document. This document describes the software used, the applied operations including parameters and the requested datasets.

³⁵ <https://roocs.github.io/>

³⁶ <https://climate.copernicus.eu/>

³⁷ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/>

³⁸ <https://xarray.dev/>

³⁹ <https://ogcapi.ogc.org/processes/>

An example of a data request and a generated PROV document can be seen in a Jupyter notebook⁴⁰ demonstrating the usage of the ROOK service. An example of the resulting provenance can be seen in its visual representation in Figure 13.

Figure 13: an example PROV document delivered by ROOCS:

The ROOK service was developed for the Copernicus Climate Data Store. A separate installation at DKRZ is also used by the **Climate4Impact** service to access subsetted data from the ESGF data pool. It is planned to use the ROOK service as a subsetting service in ESGF in general and deploy it at several sites.

6.4. Climate Data Analysis services in the ENES Community

The European Network for Earth System modelling, ENES, gathers the community working on Earth's climate system modelling with the aim to accelerate progress in this field. The community is supported by a collection of services and software, which are all together part of the ENES infrastructure (IS-ENES).

In this section we illustrate those services that started to implement provenance standards. These mostly consist of processing tools where users can perform traceable and explorative analysis of the ESGF data. Some of these tools (e.g. ESMValTool) have already contributed to the assessments of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), besides being crucial to the future reproducible elaboration of the impact of EU mitigation and adaptation policies.

6.4.1. Provenance in ESMValTool

ESMValTool⁴¹ is an open-source community-developed diagnostics and performance metrics tool for the evaluation and analysis of Earth System Models (ESMs). ESMValTool allows for a comparison of single or multiple models against predecessor versions and observations. The aim of the ESMValTool is

⁴⁰ <https://nbviewer.org/github/roocs/rooki/blob/v0.6.1/notebooks/demo/demo-rooki-weighted-average.ipynb>

⁴¹ <https://esmvaltool.org/>

to take model evaluation to the next level by facilitating analysis of many different ESM components, providing well-documented source code and scientific background of implemented diagnostics. Traceability and reproducibility of the results are ensured by providing detailed provenance records for all output.

Schematic workings

ESMValTool facilitates the evaluation of Earth System Model data as well as other climate data with a flexible approach documented in Figure 14. The user selects the data in a so-called recipe file, a text file following the yaml format which allows for the selection of important datasets in a semantic manner. This recipe file also steers the application of a large number of available pre-processors that perform common tasks for climate analysis efficiently. After the pre-processing, the data is handed over to a so-called diagnostic, that is a custom piece of code that performs more specialised analysis and usually visualisation. These diagnostics are provided by scientists and can make use of existing libraries and shared functions, leading to overall publication ready figures. Crucially, the open source development process, that includes code review from experienced developers for the technical aspects of diagnostics as well as scientists ensures the quality of code contributed to ESMValTool. This means that generally not only figures are produced, but the underlying data is stored as well, aiding greatly in reproducibility and re-use.

Figure 14. ESMValTool architecture.

Provenance tracking

The processing of recipes is achieved via the computation of individual tasks, where a task can be either a pre-processing step, or the application of a diagnostic. In this way, all the computational tasks that contribute to the recipe form a directed graph, which allows the automatic tracking of provenance

information in the following way. The input data of the recipe is identified in a standardised way, assigning identifiers to commonly used datasets such as those from the CMIP⁴² project. Every pre-processor is equipped with information about the calculations it performs, allowing accurate reflection of the individual processing steps all the way to the user-provided diagnostic. For the diagnostic, it is the individual scientist's responsibility to record adequate provenance information. However, they are greatly helped by available support functions. The end result of this careful tracking of provenance information is comprehensive information about the entire processing chain along with details about the computation environment, such as used versions of software libraries; contributing individuals, such as authors of scientific articles that underpin the developed diagnostic as well as analysts applying the given diagnostic to new datasets; and additional information, such as sources of funding.

All of this is preserved in the form of W3C PROV formatted information, available for further processing. However, it is also used by ESMValTool itself.

Provenance use

Having the provenance information available allows ESMValTool to provide a number of services for the user. This ranges from data citation to the convenient presentation of even complex sets of results that can occur in the context of larger multi-model analysis.

Via the data citation feature, ESMValTool makes it easy to credit the producers of climate data with accurate, simple identifiers where available. It also provides citation information about relevant scientific articles that form the foundation of a given analysis. Perhaps most convenient for users is the collation of all produced data files and figures in an easy to navigate overview webpage. For the crucial requirement of reproducibility, the recording of the software environment in terms of used software versions is invaluable.

Future provenance use

In the future, we hope to extend the use for provenance by harmonisation across the wider climate data analysis community, for example via the standardisation of the identification of provenance information for widely used datasets. In the long term, this will put us in a position where we can answer questions such as “What other analysis has been done with this dataset?”, “What other datasets have been analysed with the same tools?”, and similar.

6.4.2. Climate4Impact and ICCLIM Workspaces

Climate4Impact (C4I)⁴³ is a platform that enhances the discovery of climate research data available in the ESGF network, and enables experimentation within impact analysis-ready workspaces. Workspaces are managed via the SWIRRL [9], Web API that allows the automated deployment of computational virtual research environments. The API's high-level functions hide the complexity of

⁴² <https://www.wcrp-climate.org/wgcm-cmip>

⁴³ <https://www.climate4impact.eu/>

managing the underlying cloud infrastructure, thereby combining on behalf of the clients computational workflows and analysis tools on a determinate but yet extensible collection of data.

SWIRRL generates provenance information to describe the relationships between the different resources involved in the progress of the analysis. This is used to assist users in obtaining accurate reproducibility, besides delivering actionable and interoperable documentation.

This is achieved by adopting common provenance representations and technologies, already introduced in the EWC section of this document. Particularly, the PROV-Template specification and PROV-Template catalogue and the underlying Neo4j graph database, exposed by a Provenance API for interrogation and exploitation.

The provenance records cover multiple scenarios: (a) the lineage of the common workflows that incrementally populate the workspace, including updates to the data, (b) updates performed by the users to the software environment (i.e. python modules), (c) characteristics associated with the technical snapshots of a workspace that are requested by users in order to track and share reproducible progress of their research. The benefits of adopting PROV as a common and extensible data model allows SWIRRL to embed in the workflows provenance, also provenance information produced by the WPS, when these are invoked to obtain data subsets. This is possible because a few ESGF data nodes expose the ROOCS implementation of the WPS previously introduced, thereby supporting the generation of PROV documents that can be accessed and preserved by the clients. In Figure 15 we show the provenance information being accessed via the SWIRRL JupyterLab extension, which allows user to consult provenance, monitor the execution of the workflow and exploit it by trigger reproducibility actions concerning the generation of snapshots and they restore of previous states of their analysis environment.

Figure 15: SWIRRL JupyterLab extension allowing access to integrated provenance data describing workflow's lineage and environment updates.

C4I workspaces offer *icclim*⁴⁴ as default climate impact analysis module, that provides the capability to easily calculate climate indices and indicators. It is important that analysis libraries also provide

⁴⁴ icclim: <https://github.com/cerfacs-globc/icclim>

some information with respect to provenance. In the current state, provenance information is limited and is restricted to the history metadata in the NetCDF file. Here is an example for the TX90P climate index:

```
:history = "t90: [2022-04-15 14:07:47] per: percentile_doy(arr=tasmax, window=5, per=90, alpha=0.3333333333333333, beta=0.3333333333333333, copy=True) - xclim version: 0.34.3\n[2022-04-15 15:15:17] tx90p: TX90P(tasmax=tasmax, t90=per, freq='MS', bootstrap=True) - xclim version: 0.34.3\n 2022-04-15 15:15:19 Calculation of TX90p index(summer time series) from 07-16-1997 to 07-16-2010." ;
```

This history metadata is a global attribute in the NetCDF file in the CF-1.6 Convention. This capability is very limited and is not implementing W3C compliant provenance: it is rather writing the functions that are called with parameter values, so the user could eventually reproduce or know how to reproduce it. It is in the *icclim* development plan to be more W3C compliant (such as PROV-O) in how provenance information is recorded and provided.

6.4.3. Ophidia and yProv

Provenance and reproducibility are two key requirements for **climate analytics workflows** in Open Science contexts which is one of the targets of Task2.2. Handling provenance at different levels of granularity and during the entire experiment lifecycle becomes key to properly and flexibly managing lineage information related to large-scale data analysis experiments as well as enabling reproducibility scenarios, which in turn foster re-usability, one of the FAIR guiding data principles.

This section focuses on a multi-level approach [14] applied to climate data analytics experiments as a way to manage provenance information in a more structured and multifaceted way.

Specifically, two climate services are involved in the proposed use case on climate models intercomparison data analysis: **Ophidia**, a HPDA framework for scientific data analytics, and **yProv**, a novel core component for multi-level provenance management.

Figure 16: Design of the Precipitation Trend Analysis workflow

Ophidia HPDA framework

The Ophidia project [15] is a CMCC (Centro euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici) research effort on big data analytics facing scientific data analysis challenges in the climate change domain. It provides parallel (server-side) data analysis, an internal storage model and a hierarchical data organisation to manage large amounts of multidimensional scientific data. Ophidia also provides support for the implementation of complex analytics workflows [16], thus enabling users to perform a coordinated execution of multiple data analytics operators in an effective manner.

From a provenance perspective, the Ophidia framework provides a fine-grained provenance support compliant with the W3C PROV specifications, enabling scientists to drill-down into a specific task of the end-to-end workflow and get the data lineage information at a finer level of detail. In this respect, the Prov Python library⁴⁵ for the PROV Data Model is exploited to map the Ophidia core objects to the proper W3C PROV concepts, as shown in the table below.

The proposed use case on multi-model precipitation trend analysis is an example of climate models intercomparison data analysis in the CMIP context [17] and its related workflow (Figure 16) consists of hundreds of tasks (about 600).

The workflow consists of two main stages:

- A single-model step, which includes a number of identical subworkflows, each associated with a specific climate model and independent of the others.
- A multi-model step which provides the ensemble analysis on the trend comparison data gathered from the different models in the first step and produces as output five statistical indicators (maximum, minimum, average, standard deviation, and variance).

The PTA multi-model workflow has been executed on 13 models from the CMIP experiments. Datasets have been gathered from the ESGF infrastructure and downloaded at a central location at the CMCC SuperComputing Center.

Every time an Ophidia analytics operator is executed, the Ophidia framework stores the related lineage information into a memory structure; therefore, at the end of the workflow execution, it's possible to retrieve provenance documents compliant with the W3C PROV standard in several formats - JSON, XML, RDF, or graphical format - by exploiting the serialisation and deserialisation support provided by the Prov Python library.

yProv service

⁴⁵ Prov Python: <https://prov.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

yProv is a lightweight and interoperable service developed at the University of Trento to address multi-level provenance as well as reproducibility challenges in climate analytics experiments. It is designed to properly deal with the provenance space at different levels and it leverages a graph data model for the provenance information stored in the back-end.

The yProv service architecture follows a simple web-service paradigm. A client (e.g., Ophidia) connects to the web service front-end through the exposed API; the web service in turn acts as a client for the graph-database back-end, thus implementing all the needed operations to manage provenance information.

Considering the multi-model precipitation trend analysis use case proposed in the previous section, once the Ophidia service sends the JSON representation of the PROV document to yProv via the respective API call, the yProv service parses and validates the received document, and adds nodes and edges to the associated provenance graph database running on the back-end.

Figure 17. Provenance graph for the precipitation trend analysis workflow

Figure 17 shows the resulting graph for the precipitation trend analysis workflow obtained by querying the corresponding graph database and visualising the related provenance information. Input and output files are represented in blue; yellow circles represent the workflow tasks; blue circles are in-memory data acting as the output of one task and the input of the subsequent one that don't need to be stored on the file system, so they are managed in-memory by default. As it can be seen from the figure, the provenance graph consists of several repeated patterns with two branches each: these patterns describe the single-model steps of the use case. The central part of the graph represents the multi-model phase of the workflow, where the ensemble analysis, the computation of the five statistical indicators and the generation of the related maps are performed.

The above graph is just an example of a query performed against the yProv service; many other types of queries could be performed to retrieve sub-graph information and filter on the provenance level of interest, thanks to the flexible query language support provided by the graph-database technology running in the back-end. It is also worth pointing out that outputs of the queries are provided in a W3C PROV- compliant JSON representation: this ensures interoperability with other services relying on the same family of provenance standards as well as an easier integration of the yProv API into data science applications like Jupyter notebook. Also, the output graph can be queried at run-time during the workflow execution, thus providing preliminary exploratory and inspection capabilities to scientists.

The results of this work have been published in the proceedings of the 2023 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (IEEE BigData 2023) [14].

7. Discussion on Guidance and Conclusions

The document gives a broad overview on the rationale and concerns driving awareness on the importance of provenance information. The implementations gathered and briefly illustrated in this document show how existing general solutions and models have been reused and tailored to better represent the target systems. While, on the one hand all implementation demonstrate the potential for a data model as a valuable technical component to be serving different traceability purposes, on the other hand it also highlights the deep level of expertise needed for a concrete implementation, which also brings in an intrinsically and unavoidably biased view of the granularity and details to be recorded in the provenance, depending on the characteristics of the system and priority identified by their designers.

We also acknowledge that the typical happy flow of using data, thereby without events that require adjustments and updates by the downstream users, does not always highlight the benefits of implementing solutions evolving around PIDs and provenance models, which often results as a *nice to have*. It will be important to bring the evidence for a *must have*, in synchronisation with the other tasks (particularly tasks 2.1 and 2.3, on Metadata and FAIR compatibility). Introducing elements of technical guidance within the recommendations and specifications produced by international initiatives will have a high impact on the investments uptake by a single organisation. For this reason it will be crucial to collaborate with WMO and IPCC to communicate clear rationale, lessons learned and priorities concerning the transparency of climate data [20], and the importance and benefits for the end user.

We should closely study those general efforts that propose infrastructures, for environmental research [18], where provenance (and its dissemination) has a central role, as well as those global solutions that combine lineage and validation of processes in the context of monitoring and accountability of emissions⁴⁶ [13]. This should help in finding convergence in semantics and

⁴⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/blockchain-climate-action>

understanding of different roles, potential benefits and separation of concerns of the different global initiatives and implementations.

Ultimately we will work towards developing a guidance that encompasses an holistic view, obtained by engaging with the communities of users and service providers, with concrete actions that take into account priorities and perspectives on the adoption of technical enablers that foster adequate traceability of climate services, eventually in benefit of reusability and transparency.

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